

Twelve Month Report 2021

JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, BIOR, CVRL, IZSS, UNF, UH, IP, LRUJ, NPI, SDAS, COMSATS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	12 Month Report Y4 (2021)
Project Acronym	JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE
Author	Adriano Casulli
Other contributors	MEME funded partners
Due month of the report	M49
Actual submission month	49
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 10 January 2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media:
	Other recipient(s):

MEME

1. Summary of the work carried out

MEME is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively. MEME focuses on standardization, harmonization and validation of existing parasitological and molecular methods, and the development and comparative assessment of innovative molecular tools to detect Em and Eg in the food chain. Production of epidemiological data on the presence of Em/Eg eggs in the food chain focuses on vegetables for human consumption and on canine faeces in selected endemic countries. MEME provides a comprehensive set of integrative activities to harmonize procedures, improve the detection and produce epidemiological data on potential pathways of transmission of Em and Eg.

MEME current achievements:

- Production of Standard Operating Procedures and sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.
- Validation of the parasitological (Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex-PCRs and MC-RT-PCR assay) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Publications on the development and validation of new tools: a) Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for the detection of Em in stool samples; b) Bayesian Analysis of three methods for diagnosis of CE in sheep; c) Microsatellite investigations of Eg cysts; d) Species detection of Eg by novel probe-based real-time PCRs; e) Validated method based on PCR-RFLP and multiplex PCR assay for the identification of Eg species; f) Identification of Eg G1/G3 by SNPs assays.
- Ongoing multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments (contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces).
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).

MEME scientific papers published on peer-review journals:

- [Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone](#). *Pathogens*. 2021;10(10):1326.
- [New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030](#). *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021;15(5):e0009373.
- [Identification of *Echinococcus granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs genotyping assays](#). *Pathogens*. 2021;10(2):125.
- [Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs \(*Acinonyx jubatus*\) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed *Besnoitia* species](#). *Parasit Vectors*. 2021;14(1):201.
- [Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the stool samples of naturally Infected red foxes](#). *Animals (Basel)*. 2020;10(12):2381.
- [Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia \(Italy\)](#). *Pathogens*. 2020;9(6):907.
- [A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level](#). *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 2020;85:104575.
- [Bayesian analysis of three methods for diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in sheep](#). *Pathogens*. 2020;9(10):796.

- [Species detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex by novel probe-based real-time PCRs.](#) *Pathogens.* 2020;9(10):791.
- [microsatellite investigations of multiple *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans.](#) *Pathogens.* 2020;9(6):444.
- [Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.](#) *The Lancet Global Health.* 2020;8(4):e470-e471.

2. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Sampling strategy

JRP18-WP1-T1. SOPs for sampling in matrices

The following Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were generated:

- Sampling of faecal material in dog faeces collected from the environment (WP1-T2) and their processing for molecular analysis.
- Sampling of *E. granulosus* cysts from naturally infected sheep and pigs at abattoirs (WP1-T2) and experimentally infected sheep (WP1-T3) and their processing for molecular analyses.
- Sampling of faeces and small/large intestines from experimentally infected foxes (WP1-T3) and their processing for parasitological and molecular analyses.
- Sampling of vegetables for human consumption (WP3-T6) and their processing for molecular analysis.

Task accomplished.

JRP18-WP1-T2. Matrices collection in the field from intermediate and definitive hosts

The aim of this task was to collect different parasitic matrices from naturally infected definitive and intermediate hosts for their use in other WPs. Involved participants organized sampling from definitive and intermediate animal hosts. Totally, 590 intestines of red foxes, 181 intestines of arctic foxes, 100 intestines of raccoon dogs from endemic areas were collected; most of them were examined with SCT/SSCT. From positive intestines, Em worms were isolated. Intestines and isolated worms will be used for tasks connected with new PCRs and SSCT validation, and PTs organization. Additionally, faeces from distal part of large intestine were collected. A total of 63 red fox intestines from areas supposed to be free of Em were collected and 300 intestines of red foxes from Em free areas (Ireland) were collected. Other parasites (*Mesocestoides* spp., *Taenia* spp.) were isolated from the intestines of red foxes for specificity controls. A total of 210 samples of pigs' livers and 200 sheep's livers with suggestive lesions of *Echinococcus* spp. larvae were collected and prepared for identification. Additionally, few Em and *Taenia hydatigena* lesions isolated from *Arvicola terrestris* and Eg cysts isolated from sheep and pigs were collected. A total of 70 sibling voles were examined for Em with only one showing parasitic liver cysts (probably *Taenia* spp. A total of 1,304 faecal samples from dogs for epidemiological study were collected. Additionally, hundreds dog faecal samples from environment were collected as a potential matrix for validation. Task accomplished.

JRP18-WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models

Concerning the fox model, four infections were realized with two foxes euthanized and the two others were dewormed after 90 dpi. Worms (training on SSCT, WP4-T1), eggs (lettuce investigations, WP3-T6) and faeces were obtained. Interruptions due to COVID-19 disrupted the production of protoscoleces in the mouse model currently delaying the possibility of infecting foxes. The experimental material currently available consists of 5,000 Em eggs, 50 faeces and 100 microtubes of frozen protoscoleces. Ethical authorisation on "Experimental infection of carnivores with *Echinococcus multilocularis*" (Decree n° 21_105#33541 November 16 2021, APAFIS #33541-202110081648536 v11) has been renewed for five

years. Task accomplished.

WP2. Validation of parasitological and molecular assays

JRP18-WP2-T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT

Among the 603 red and arctic fox intestines collected by five partners (NVI, PIWET, FLI, ANSES and BIOR), 568 were independently analysed for each of the four segments of intestines resulting in 139 positive samples. The remaining 35 red fox intestines collected by FLI will be analysed in February 2022 (M50) with the aim of obtaining more positive intestines for the estimate of the sensitivity of SSCT method. The protocol of validation for SSCT was also applied to raccoon dogs from Poland and Latvia in order to determine a potential combination of a pair of segments which may result in a high sensitivity of the method. Among 70 racoon dog intestines which were analysed, five were infected by Em. Data from racoon dogs will be combined with those from experimental results previously obtained in red foxes. Task almost accomplished.

JRP18-WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs

This task focused on the validation of two molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. in definitive and intermediate hosts, targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers:

- Assay 1: Boubaker et al. (PLoS Negl Trop Dis, 2013); a single-tube multiplex PCR allowing discrimination of *Echinococcus* at species/genotypes level.
- Assay 2: Trachsel et al. (Parasitology, 2007); a single-tube multiplex PCR targeting the definitive host for the identification of eggs belonging to Eg, Em and *Taenia* genus.

Assay 1. Validation process was developed as follows: first, a collection of reference parasitic material (worms, cysts and genomic DNA), provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis](#) (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included at least two or more parasitic materials for each species of the Eg complex, for Em and for members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they resulted in an unequivocal species identification and were confirmed by three independent repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay have been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The assay was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors, resulting in the lack of six over 11 PCR targets needed for proper species identification. Thus, results were evaluated again under several modified conditions (i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). Last, single primer pairs were tested independently to evaluate their performance and, when their working conditions were found proper, they were combined with other primer pairs to achieve a balanced amplification. In conclusion, lack of specific PCR bands or the appearance of aspecific PCR bands made impossible to execute the multiplex PCR and to get simultaneously all the targeted markers amplified, neither with the original conditions nor with the modifications tried. The high number of PCR markers targeted (n=11) by Assay 1 probably had a negative impact on the overall performance of this method.

Assay 2. The original paper describes a Multiplex PCR, which amplifies fragments of different sizes of DNA encoding portions of the mitochondrial genes (Subunit I of NADH dehydrogenase (ND1) for Em (PCR fragment 395 bp), and portions of ribosomal genes, subunit rrnS for Eg complex (117 bp), *Taenia* spp. (267 bp) and *Diphyllobotrium* spp. (267 bp). The original multiplex PCR was developed to identify eggs of the taeniid tapeworms from carnivores. In this validation process genomic DNA extracted from worms (Em and *Taenia* spp.) and cyst material (Eg) served as template for the multiplex PCR assay.

The validation process was developed as reported in assay 1. First, a collection of reference DNA, provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and](#)

Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included DNA for the species of Eg, Em and members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*, *T. polyacanta*, *T. hydatigena*, *Diphyllobotrium latum* and *Diphyllobotrium dendriticum*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they were specific (unequivocal species identification) and confirmed by three independent repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay has been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The multiplex-PCR was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors. Gel electrophoresis resulted in the following results: Em amplicon showed the characteristic band of *Taenia* (267 bp), *Taenia* spp. amplicon always showed a non-specific band (around 200 bp), and the amplicon of Eg was often weak. Mixed infections were excluded by the nature of the matrices used, therefore the results were evaluated again under several modified conditions (i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). After several tests, the concentration of the primers was changed to an equimolar primer mix (final concentration 0.2 μ M), which resulted in a correct identification of all species. Expanding the number of Em DNA tested (n=82) from different countries it was observed that 10 out of 82 samples showed the typical band of Em but also a light band typical of Eg (117 bp). In conclusion, the single-tube multiplex PCR by Trachsel and colleagues (2007) has been proved to be a robust and reliable assay that can be used not only for the identification of taeniid eggs but extended to DNA extracted from different matrices. Nonetheless, problems with specificity of the PCR products can be eventually observed and the optimization of the primer concentration must be achieved. In this validation process an equimolar (0.2 μ M) primer mix showed the highest efficiency for the PCR reaction. Task accomplished.

JRP18-WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay

Two magnetic capture protocols, published by Isaksson et al., 2014 (10.1186/s13071-014-0583-6), and Maas et al., 2016 (10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.10.016), respectively, were performed in parallel in two laboratories (FLI and RIVM) using the artificially spiked fox faecal samples. The reproducibility of the methods and their analytical sensitivity were tested and compared in the two laboratories. In addition, these two methods were tested with a set of field faecal samples from foxes naturally infected with Em. Thus, diagnostic sensitivity of the two methods was also tested and compared. The data obtained are currently being analysed and written up in a manuscript.

SOP for validation of Magnetic capture – real-time PCR assay. There was a delay with the milestone in this task and the lead on the task was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEME in 2021) to NVI in M37. The methods (DNA extraction with automatic washing and manual washing protocols, as well as three real-time PCR protocols) and accompanying training video (for magnetic capture DNA extraction with manual washing) were published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes in M42 (DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.4897969; 10.5281/zenodo.4746190; 10.5281/zenodo.4746181; 10.5281/zenodo.4746141). If needed additional guidance, via digital meeting platforms, has been offered to the seven laboratories (BIOR, CVRL, INIAV, ISS, PIWET, SSI and VFL) that have registered for the training. So far, only one has requested this. The verification and ring test material has been distributed to all partners that have registered for participation in the ring test (FLI, INIAV, ISS, NVI, SSI and RIVM). So far only one of the partners has provided their ring test results whilst three others have requested a delay to reporting due to supply chain issues for the reagents used or request for additional training in 2022. The ring test consists of a sample set of 10 faecal samples that have potentially been spiked with Em worm segments for each laboratory to analyse. This task is anticipated to be completed during the first half of 2022.

WP3. Development validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments

JRP18-WP3-T1. New molecular markers for Em and Eg s.l.: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution

ST1: new mitochondrial markers. Recent studies have revealed an unexpectedly high genetic diversity at mitochondrial genome level for Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto* and *E. canadensis* - genotypes G6/G7). However, these studies covered only part of the genetic diversity since many important endemic regions were missing (e.g. China and Russia). Moreover, for several species including Em, the mitogenomes data are scarce. In order to develop species/genotype specific diagnostic assays, additional mitogenomes data are required for all *Echinococcus* spp. using a larger worldwide panel of different Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) species and genotypes (n=300), and Em (n=200). Toehold Exchange Probes based diagnostic tool will be developed to provide a reliable and rapid identification of species/genotypes of Eg (*E. granulosus sensu lato*) and Em. The complete mitogenomes of 48 samples of the Eg genotypes G6/G7 from various countries of the World were sequenced. These sequences will be included to the total dataset of mitogenomes.

ST2: New microsatellite markers. The screening of the Eg genome resulted in the identification of 15 new microsatellites targets, which are currently evaluated for their polymorphism, reproducibility, limit of detection, quality of the electrophoretic profiles and their specificity. The selected targets will be coupled with EgSca6 microsatellite previously described by MEME (M'Rad et al., 2020) in order to obtain a panel with a high discriminatory power. The possibility to use these microsatellites for large phylogenetic studies was initiated for the validation of the clustering method. Eg DNA samples from North Africa (Morocco and Tunisia) and Europe (France and Moldova) were collected and testing of microsatellites polymorphism is ongoing. Four new microsatellite targets were identified and are currently under evaluation.

ST3: NGS-based method. The very high variability of Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) at the mitogenome level provides a possibility to perform source attribution analysis. Using the mitogenome data together with microsatellite fingerprinting may constitute reliable means to track the source of infection. Previous studies have shown that samples collected from the same area can be distinguished from samples from other areas based on complete or near-complete mitogenome data. At first, a method will be developed to sequence 96 mitogenomes with a single sequencing run. For this, we have already developed primers that enable PCR-amplification of the entire mitogenome in a single PCR. We aim to use 96 different barcodes and the PacBio's Single Molecule, Real-Time (SMRT) Sequencing in the Sequel System, which allows easy and cost effective generation of highly accurate long reads (>99% single-molecule read accuracy) for DNA amplicons, such as the complete mitochondrial genomes. However, this assay requires samples of good quality. As the quality of parasite samples varies and often important samples are of low quality, we started to develop primers for such samples that consists of several primer pairs. Testing of these primers is in progress and task will be accomplished in due time.

JRP18-WP3-T2. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg s.l. and Em

We established six TaqMan® probe-based qPCRs that can be used for the diagnosis of Em and Eg genotypes in five epidemiologically relevant species and subgroups, i.e. *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 to G8 and G10), a single genotype (G8) of the *E. canadensis* cluster as a single-step genotyping technique. It also allows differentiating Eg and Em samples from other *Echinococcus* spp. or *Taenia* spp. in samples derived from cystic or faecal material. The qPCRs show high efficiency (ranging between 99% and 106%), high analytical specificity (100%) and sensitivity (ranging between 0.6 and 1.4 copies/μl), when used with DNA

obtained from cysts or from cloned PCR products. Therefore, they are suitable for a PCR-based diagnosis of CE in intermediate hosts, including humans as dead-end hosts. To parallelize the detection and typing of members of the Eg complex, two variants of a TaqMan® probe-based five-plex real-time qPCR assay were developed and validated. The first variant of these assays can simultaneously detect and genotype *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), and the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10). The second variant of the test is capable of detecting and distinguishing *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* genotype G8, and the remaining two members of the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 and G10). For simultaneous diagnosis and typing of Eg complex and Em infections, further variants of a TaqMan® probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR are currently being developed. Task accomplished.

JRP18-WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS

First step was to establish a pipeline for nanopore mtDNA sequencing and to allow sufficient data generation and for testing data analysis tools. Work started using DNA from positive controls included from the MC-DNA EmNok surveillance method, as these were spiked faecal samples isolated using magnetic capture of mtDNA from Em. The processed samples contained lower number of targets compared with pure Em-controls. Having enough material to allow sequencing, in order to get nanopore protocols working, call for some modifications of the material. As an alternative enrichment step, Illustra TempliPhi, was considered as a means to generate more template DNA for nanopore sequencing. A few dilutions were carried out to accommodate for faint samples. In addition to the positive Em control from MC method, a standard prepared DNA samples from *Taenia* spp. were also included as controls. Samples were cleaned and DNA was measured. Further, they were prepared according to the selected nanopore sequence kit and some runs on Minion flongle flowcell was attempted on the products. All runs failed to generate data, and experiments were suspended until replacement chemicals arrived. As an alternative approach which would help solve the potential issue of not having enough parasite DNA molecules available in the sample to allow for full characterisation, and learning from recent method development for Sars-Cov2, a similar approach to the nanopore Midnight protocol (Freed et al., 2020) which is in use for full characterisation of virus genomes. We are exploring a similar long PCR-tiling approach for *Echinococcus* spp. mtDNA characterisation, using a panel of primers generating eight overlapping segments. This protocol will be tested on positive samples (native parasites, and fish-DNA) and PCR-optimisation and testing suitable nanopore kit protocols (ligation vs. rapid) is ongoing.

JRP18-WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma

We encounter technical difficulties regarding the proteomic study (at ISS, Italy) from plasma of experimentally infected (and controlled) sheep in Portugal (at INIAV, Portugal). Because of COVID-19, we were late in obtaining ethics committee approval at INIAV. Afterwards, in November 2020 we made two attempts with parasite protoscoleces collected from sheep in Sardinia (IZSS, Italy) to infect foxes in Nancy, France (ANSES) where ethics committee approval was also obtained for foxes. Unfortunately, in January 2021 we did not obtain Eg worms from fox experimental model (neither at flotation of faecal samples nor at PCR examination). During February/august 2021 we mobilized the international community to provide Eg eggs from experimentally or naturally infected canids. We received positive feedback from Australia, Iraqi Kurdistan, Kazakhstan and China, willing to collect and subsequently provide eggs. National lockdowns and national restrictions due to COVID-19 affected such field-collaboration since all these participants have retired. These eggs would have been used to infect sheep (animals are still housed in Portugal) and collect plasma for proteomic analyses searching for biomarkers of infection. We also discussed to modify ethical clearance at INIAV and try to infect sheep with Eg protoscoleces, instead of Eg egg. Since intraperitoneal injection of protoscoleces does not mimic natural infection, this may affect molecular pathways and therefore proteomic analysis outcome. Even if we found

another solution, there would be no time to implement it before the end of MEME because of the long time (at least 1 year) it takes for the parasite to develop in sheep. We confirm that COVID19-pandemic has definitively discontinued task 4 of WP3.

JRP18-WP3-T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques

The different molecular methods developed in MEME (RFLP and qPCR for Eg; see MEME publications) will be compared with already available methods regarding limit of detection of each assay but also by evaluating sensitivity and specificity using DNA samples obtained from field samples but also from experimental infection. Furthermore, faecal samples obtained during SSCT will be used to be compared with results obtained by processing the available Em copro-qPCR. This evaluation will be realized using the same DNA samples in different laboratories. Task will be accomplished in due time.

JRP18-WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg

The filtration method (Guggisberg et al., 2020) combined with real-time PCR in lettuces was validated at ANSES with 95% probability of detection for three Em eggs (75% probability of detection for two eggs and 50% for one egg). A first survey conducted in 2020 in France collected 106 lettuce samples (grouped in 35 pooled samples; each pool constituted from two to five lettuces from the same geographical origin). Seventeen pooled samples were from private kitchen gardens (n=44), while 18 from local markets (n=62). Em was detected in two pooled samples from local markets and one from kitchen gardens. *Hydatigera* spp. (cat tapeworm) was detected in four and two pooled samples from kitchen gardens and local markets, respectively. In the summer of 2021, a survey was conducted in Europe, including 15 MEME partners from 12 endemic countries for Em and/or Eg. Around 1,200 lettuce samples were collected from local markets and supermarkets with around 50/100 lettuces collected by each partner which realized the first washing step of the filtration method. In order to minimize bias, these frozen pellets were sent to ANSES where filtration and molecular detection methods are undergoing. One Em positive pooled sample out of 60 tested (n=120 lettuces) was identified in France, one positive pooled sample out of 44 (n=88 lettuces) was identified in Switzerland and two positive pooled samples out of 25 were identified in Denmark (n=50 lettuces). No positive Em samples were detected in pooled samples from Portugal (n=100 lettuces), Germany (n=62 lettuces) and The Netherlands (n=6 lettuces). A new additional subtask on the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. eggs in strawberries and blueberries was inserted in MEME. The filtration method was validated on strawberries with 95% probability of detection of three eggs in 200g sample (88% probability of detection for both two and one egg) and will be validated for blueberries in 2022. A survey started in France in 2021 with 34 samples of strawberries collected from local markets, which resulted negative to Em. This study is planned to be extended in 2022 by including samples of blueberries from other countries. Task will be accomplished in due time.

JRP18-WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas

Eight MEME partners were involved in this task (one of them left the task because of COVID-19 pandemic). Until now 1,304 samples of dog faeces were collected, most of them together with filled questionnaires. About 380 more samples are planned to be collected before the end of this study. DNA was extracted from 1,056 samples. Overall, 355 samples have already been examined in France, Italy, Poland using multiplex PCR (Trachsel et al., 2007) and no *Echinococcus* spp. positive were detected. In France, 1 *Taenia krabbei*, 1 *Taenia serialis* and 1 *Mesocestoides* spp. positive samples were recorded. In Italy, 60 samples were additionally examined with the new qPCRs (Maksimov et al., 2020) for Eg complex developed within MEME framework; 15% positive results were obtained. Additionally, in France, 109 samples were examined using qPCR (Knapp et al., 2016) for Em but without positive results. The expected end of the task is M54.

JRP18-WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires

Due to COVID-19 impact on hospitals, we replaced this task with "Human source attribution of cerebral CE by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature". This task focuses on the first source attribution based on molecular methods of a rare case of cerebral CE in a child from Roman campagna. A literature search was also conducted on 6 databases with Boolean terms for the clinical and epidemiological quantification of cerebral CE at global level. No limitation of year of publication was envisaged. Inclusion criteria were: clinical reports including case reports, case series, clinical trials, retrospective and prospective cases of confirmed human cerebral CE. Exclusion criteria were: animal cases, AE cases and no confirmed cases of cerebral CE. The search identified 1,776 relevant articles which were selected by title and abstract. Relevant data from full text of 422 papers were currently extracted. Task will be accomplished in due time.

WP4. Training, dissemination and proficiency testing schemes

JRP18-WP4-T1. Trainings

This WP focuses on establishing the most effective methods for training scientists from institutions participating to MEME in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, no physical training was conducted until now. For this reason, NVI generated online training on "Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps". A training movie showing each of the steps can be viewed on YouTube at: <https://www.youtube.com/embed/hdo3mE8oMKE?rel=0>. One of the partners (ISS) has requested physical training for the magnetic capture method at NVI and this has been planned for spring/summer 2022.

JRP18-WP4-T2. Dissemination of project results

This task focuses on establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results at different levels. Due to COVID-19 pandemic non-participation to physical events prevent the dissemination, while it was done during online events ("One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021", "Annual meeting of the European Reference Laboratory for Parasites 2020" and "13th European Multicollloquium of Parasitology") and publishing scientific papers for a wide scientific audience (see papers on *Lancet Global Health* and *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*).

JRP18-WP4-T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3

A Proficiency Testing scheme (PT) on "Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT)" for the detection of Em was launched in October 2021 (M46). Such PT involved 12 participants from MEME and two additional European national reference laboratories out of MEME. The participants have received five segments of intestines (three negative and two positive) in order to perform SSCT. A discordant result was obtained by two participants (one false negative and one false positive). These results can be considered as very encouraging as any laboratory realized SSCT in routine diagnostic intestinal analysis (excepting organizer Anses) and many don't even use intestinal diagnostic as a routine method for detection in definitive host. A second PT on "Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test" is planned and this task will be completed during the first half of 2022.

WP5. Scientific and administrative management

JRP18-WP5-T1. Setup of the project

Task accomplished.

JRP18-WP5-T2. Administrative and scientific management

Activities are ongoing throughout the lifespan of MEME to accomplish its administrative and scientific management.

JRP18-WP5-T3. Ethics management

All ethic needs of MEME accomplished.

3. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/10/10/1326 https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.Ydr55ybSlzk	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)
New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373 https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOOgp	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited editorial)
Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907 https://zenodo.org/record/4159681	YES		Yes, 1.389 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo	YES		Yes, 2.190 €
Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122381 https://zenodo.org/record/4384600	YES		Yes, 1.481 €
Species detection within the <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex by novel probe based Real-Time PCRs. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791 https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.258,81 €
A validated method to identify <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> at species level. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575 https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc	YES		Yes, 2.300 €

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Identification of <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125 https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZM0	YES		Yes, 696,38 €
Bayesian analysis to evaluate three diagnostic methods for cystic echinococcosis in sheep. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796 https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.389,79 €
Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto</i> cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444 https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0	YES		Yes, 654,56 €
Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8 https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited comment)